

Strengthening Data-driven Health and Life Sciences in the Netherlands: the role of TDCC-LSH

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Abstract

The Thematic Digital Competence Centre for Life Sciences and Health (TDCC-LSH) was established in September 2022 to advance digital practices within the life sciences and biomedical/health sciences in the Netherlands. TDCC-LSH operates as one of the three national-level TDCCs, initiated by the Dutch Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure. TDCC-LSH aims to strengthen and harmonize digital practices across the life sciences and biomedical/health sciences domains.

TDCC-LSH is driven by three main ambitions: to harmonize data stewardship and data access practices, enhance the interoperability of digital solutions and resources, and strengthen capacity and expertise in digital research. To achieve these goals, TDCC-LSH collaborates with a broad network of stakeholders, including Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research Support Organisations (RSOs), National Large Scale Research Infrastructures (LSRIs), and international connections like ELIXIR and EOSC.

In its initial phase, TDCC-LSH focused on strengthening relationships with major LSH community initiatives, a.o. the LSRIs, the Dutch UMCs, ELIXIR-NL and BioSB. TDCC-LSH has also initiated several community-based projects, including the development of a FAIR Fellowship program for LSH data stewards, building an LSH FAIR trainers network, developing a FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows, and extending the BioSB course programme with AI-training for LSH data scientists. These projects and initiatives underscore TDCC-LSH's commitment to fostering a robust digital ecosystem.

Looking ahead, TDCC-LSH will concentrate on implementing and executing its projects, further solidifying its role as a platform that connects major initiatives and expert communities to strengthen data-driven health and life sciences in the Netherlands.

References

1. van Gelder, C. W. G., Zwiers, K., Schoots, F., & Kok, R. (2024). Strengthening the Dutch data driven health & life sciences field: TDCC-LSH facts and figures September 2022- August 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14292810>